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Effects of Co-operative and Competitive Learning Approaches on Secondary School Economics Students' Achievement in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effects of cooperative learning approaches on students' achievement in economics in senior secondary schools in Jalingo education zone, Taraba state. Two research questions were raised and two research hypotheses formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. This study adopted quasi-experimental research design. The sample of the study consisted of 5030 SSII Economics students made up 230 girls and 270 boys from 5 schools across Jalingo Education Zone. The population of this study comprised of 6.139 SSII students in more than 28 Public Secondary schools in the Zone. Two research instruments were used for the data collection. The instruments were tagged; Economics Achievement Questions (EATQ) and Instructional Learning Strategy Questionnaire (ILSQ). Descriptive Statistical tool of mean and standard deviation was used to analyze the research questions while for the hypotheses, the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) and T-Test statistical tools were used. The result showed that both competitive and comparative learning strategies, provide; equal treatments for all students, counselling and encouragement to students of Economics irrespective of gender.

Keywords: cooperative learning, students' achievement, senior secondary schools

INTRODUCTION

Economics is a science which deals with the judicious utilization of scarce resources. Economics has been identified as an important subject through which the technological development of a country can be attained and no nation can develop without the knowledge and managerial skills of Economics (Dada, 2019). The knowledge of Economics provides a learner with the opportunities to live meaningfully within the changing world. The main objective of learning Economics are to: equip student with the basic skills and principles necessary for useful living and higher education, prepare and encourage students to be prudent and effective in the management of scarce resources, raise students respect for the dignity of labour and appreciation of cultural and social value of our own society, and to enable student acquire knowledge for the practical solution of the society.

The study of Economics further enables students to understand the nature of the complexity of the Economic activity in which they are a very small part. It enables students to understand and appreciate various government policies where choices have to be made such as probably to spend more money on free education. It also provides the students with the basic skills for analyzing economic problems thereby preparing them better for position where economic decisions have to be made. The study of Economics helps government to promote growth and development thereby leading to improvement of the quality of life of the citizen. The study

of Economics is also useful to understand and alter the inequalities in the distribution of income and opportunities.

Despite the relevance of Economics to everyday life in the area of commerce and industry, the teaching of the subject in Nigeria and particularly in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State is characterized by many inadequacies such as few instructional materials, lac of audio-visual aids, poor teaching methods and others. These have actually affected the effectiveness of Economics teachers (Colak, 2015).

Enrolment of students in the subject has been increasing year after year, however students' performance at the exit level of the West African Examination Council (WAEC), National Examination Council (NECO) and National Board for Technical Education Certificate (NABTEB) remain very poor. It has also been observed that the achievement of candidates in Economics is not only poor but continue to fall over the years in a study on an 'appraisal of trends in achievement of students in Economics at the Senior Secondary Certificate Examination in Oyo State (Adebowole, Loyode & Ojo, 2017). To overcome this challenge, Economics education researchers have observed that co-operative learning and competitive learning approaches can be used to improve student performance in Economics. Several researchers had been conducted by Economics educators (Ajiboye, 2015) and the results agree that these learning approaches are really effective.

Okereke (2019) provided several benefits on the use of cooperative learning approach for students. These benefits are: promotion of deep learning of materials. Students achieve better grades in cooperative learning as a result of sharing ideas, varying of social skills and civic values, students learn higher-order, critical thinking skills, promotion of personal growth and development of positive attitudes toward autonomous learning. In other words, cooperative learning has the potential to engage students actively through cognitive and social encounters that foster collegial and collective thinking whereby generating infused knowledge at a higher level of cognitive thinking and deliberation through attitudinal change and motivational influences within the context of classroom based teaching and learning.

In like manner, competitive learning strategy as contended by Johnson and Johnson, (2016), brings a variable into the equation that shifts the participants attention to the cost of their performance in the task. The purpose of the activity moves from the learning goals to efficiency, speed, and the outcome relative to others.

Furthermore, introducing competitive learning strategy into the classroom brings a shift in students' attitude. It gives students an air of importance and motivates them to perform better, especially when rewards are attached to it (Emmer & Gerwels 2016). In using competitive learning strategy, the grouped students tend to place increased value on the outcomes of their efforts and tend to decrease their focus on the process. That is, students will increase attention on what it takes to outshine others and decrease attention on learning for its own sake. Competitive element has an effect on a group dynamics because it is often motivated by a competition that develops creativity and problems solving skills.

In this study, competitive learning strategy is used where students work in subgroups. Members of each subgroup work strictly on their own, strive to be the best in the sub-group. The competitive learning strategy in teaching Economics provides a combination of learning opportunities and chance to have fun on the part of students. Students do not fear the potential consequences which is a good indicator that competitive learning strategy initiates social skills and managerial abilities (Emininmow, 2016).

In short, competitive learning strategy is about teaching students how to learn without fear of failure or letting their ego become too involved. Students can access the joy of the moment, involvement, challenge, adventure, and suspense can be fun if students feel free and the situation supports fun over comparison. Fun during this learning strategy occurs when students see competition as the game, the fleeting reality and the learning relationships, and self-respect as the lasting reality (Parveen 2017). The importance of cooperative learning strategy and competitive learning strategy in the achievement of student's performance cannot be over emphasized. It is on this background that this study is anchored.

Economics is one of the core subjects in the Senior Secondary School curriculum which reflects the recognition of the vital role the subject plays in contemporary society. Olatunde (2019) posited that the present day teaching and learning of Economics is far from being satisfactory. Scholars blame poor performance of students in Economics on poor methods and approaches to teaching which have reduced the level of students' motivation. Also, the performance of students in Economics in Taraba State for the past ten years (2014-2022) at the credit

level, from the Chief Examiners' reports of the West African Examination Council (WAEC) shows that the students performed poorly. Statistics from WAEC also show that the declining performance also applies to the November/December West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE).

Researchers in Economics education have identified some factors responsible for this mass failure and poor performance in Economics. Top of the factor is the teaching method. To overcome the challenges posed by the teaching and learning method, experts have advocated the use of cooperative and competitive learning approaches in the study of the subject. It is against this backdrop that the researcher is carrying out this study in other to find solution to the causes of poor performance in Economics in Jalingo Education Zone in Taraba State

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to determine the effects of cooperative and competitive learning approaches on students academic achievement test in Economics among Senior Secondary Schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State, Nigeria.

Specifically, the study seeks to:

- i. determine the mean difference between Economics Academic Achievement Test of students' exposed to cooperative learning and those exposed to competitive learning strategy among Senior Secondary School students in Jalingo Educational Zone, Taraba State.
- ii. determine interactive effects of gender and instructional approaches on the Economics Achievement Test of students in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were used to guide the study.

- i. Is there any significant effect of gender on students achievement in Economics using cooperative and Cooperative Learning approaches in Jalingo Education Zone?
- ii. Is there any interactive effects of gender and instructional approaches on students achievement in Economics in senior secondary school students in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to direct the study. All the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female Economics students exposed to cooperative learning strategy and those exposed to competitive learning strategy.
- H₀₂: There is no significant interaction effect of gender and instructional approaches on students achievement in Economics.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research design used in this study was the post-test quasi-experimental design. Population of the study comprised of 6,139 senior secondary II Economics students from 28 public secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State. The sample of the study consisted of 500 SSII Economics students. Out of these 500 SSII Economics students, 100 were from Lau, 100 from Ardo-kola and 300 from Jalingo Local Government Areas. Two instruments used for data collection were tagged Instructional Learning Strategy Questionnaire (ILSQ), and Economics Achievement test Questions (EATQ). Three experts validated the instrument two in Educational Measurement and Evaluation and the other one in Economics education. The reliability index yielded 0.78. The data collected were analyzed using the descriptive statistical tool of mean and standard deviation and inferential statistical tool of analysis of covariance ANCOVA and T-test.

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Research question one: *Is there any significant effect of gender on students' achievement in Economics using cooperative and competitive learning approaches?*

Table 1: Independent t-test Analysis of the mean ratings of male and female students' achievement in Economics using cooperative and competitive learning approaches

Cooperative and competitive learning approaches	N	\bar{x}	SD	t-cal
Male	270	41.26	1.95	57.15*
Female	230	33.45	1.03	

*Significant at .05 level; df = 498, p-value = .000

From Table 1, the calculated t-value of 57.15 was found to be higher than the p-value of .000 needed at 0.05 level of significance, with 498 degree of freedom. Since the calculated t-value was less than the p-value, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is a significant effect of gender on students' achievement in Economics using cooperative and competitive learning approaches.

Research Question two: *Is there any interactive effect of gender and instructional approaches on students achievement in Economics?*

To answer this research question, the mean ratings of the interactive effect of gender and instructional approaches on students achievement in Economics were compared using independent t-test statistic and the result is presented in Table 5

Table 2. Independent t-test Analysis of the mean ratings of the interactive effect of gender and instructional approaches

Interactive effect	N	\bar{x}	SD	t-cal
Male	270	35.48	2.33	23.90
Female	230	30.78	2.07	

*Significant at .05 level; df = 498, p-value = .000

From Table 2, the calculated t-value of 23.90 was found to be higher than the p-value of .000 needed at 0.05 level of significance, with 498 degree of freedom. Since the calculated t-value was higher than the p-value, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies there is interactive effect of gender and instructional approaches on students' achievement in Economics.

Hypothesis one: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female Economics students exposed to cooperative learning strategy and those exposed to competitive learning strategy.

Table 3. Analysis of Covariance of difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female Economics students exposed to cooperative learning strategy and those exposed to competitive learning strategy.

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: Posttest

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	32640.186(a)	50	652.804	105.620	.000
Intercept	1651.827	1	1651.827	267.257	.000
Pretest	209.741	1	209.741	33.935	.000
Cooperative	2927.928	13	225.225	36.440	.000
Competitive	3958.769	15	263.918	42.701	.000
Gender	.507	1	.507	.082	.775
Cooperative * Competitive	.000	0	.	.	.
Cooperative * gender	23.923	6	3.987	.645	.694
Competitive * gender	29.186	6	4.864	.787	.580
Cooperative * Competitive * gender	.000	0	.	.	.
Error	2775.116	449	6.181		
Total	458413.000	500			
Corrected Total	35415.302	499			

a R Squared = .922 (Adjusted R Squared = .913)

The result of the analysis as presented in Table 3 revealed the main effect of gender and students' achievement when taught using Cooperative * Competitive method was not significant ($F = .000$; $P > .05$); the 'method main effect was significant for Cooperative ($F = 36.440$; $P < .05$) and Competitive method was significant ($F = 42.701$; $df 2$ and 497 ; $P < .05$). The null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female Economics students exposed to cooperative learning strategy and those exposed to competitive learning strategy was retained with respect to gender and a combination of method and gender was retained for method. This result implies that there is a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female Economics students exposed to cooperative learning strategy and those exposed to competitive learning strategy.

Hypothesis two: There is no significant interaction effect of gender and instructional approaches on students achievement in Economics.

TABLE 4

Analysis of Covariance of the interaction effect of gender and instructional approaches on students achievement in Economics.

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: Posttest

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	27149.043(a)	3	9049.681	543.008	.000
Intercept	377.187	1	377.187	22.632	.000
Pretest	26879.018	1	26879.018	1612.821	.000
Gender	55.680	1	55.680	3.341	.068
approaches	56.065	1	56.065	3.364	.067
gender * approaches	.000	0	.	.	.
Error	8266.259	496	16.666		
Total	458413.000	500			
Corrected Total	35415.302	499			

a R Squared = .767 (Adjusted R Squared = .765)

The result of the analysis as presented in Table 4 revealed that the main interaction effect of gender and instructional approaches on students' achievement in Economics was not significant ($F = .000$; $P > .05$); the approaches main effect was significant ($F = 3.364$; $P < .05$) and the interaction of gender was significant ($F = 3.341$ df 2 and 221; $P < .05$). The null hypothesis was retained with respect to gender and a combination of method and gender was rejected for method. This result implies that there is no significant interaction effect of gender and instructional approaches on students' achievement in Economics.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This section is devoted to the discussion of findings of the hypotheses formulated to direct the study. This discussion is presented hypothesis by hypothesis.

Gender and Achievement in Economics in Senior Secondary School Students

The findings of the third hypothesis indicated that there is a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female Economics students exposed to cooperative learning strategy and those exposed to competitive learning strategy. The finding of this hypothesis is contrarily with the view of Umar et al, (2015) who indicated that there was no significant difference between gender and Academic Performance in Colleges of Education in Borno State in favour of female students. The similarities between this research and the reviewed one is that both used male and female variables, both used Achievement Test instruments for their work. While this present research is in Taraba State, the reviewed was in Borno State. The present study is in secondary school while the reviewed was in colleges of education. The present study is using quasi-experimental research design while the reviewed used the survey research design.

Uwanciya, (2017) also noted that gender differences in academic performance of students studying Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) subjects at the University of Ghana Using a mixed-methods research design, this study compares academic performance of males and females studying STEM subjects or courses at the university level with that of the senior high school level performance. The factors contributing to the gender differences in academic performance at the two levels of the educational ladder were also explored. Overall, the results show that the academic performance of males was better than females at the senior high school level, whilst at the tertiary level, the academic performance of females appeared to have improved relative to that of males. Whilst gender stereotypes contributed greatly to differences in academic performance at the high school level, factors such as teaching methodologies and styles, motivation and support from parents, and advocacy campaigns on women's empowerment accounted for the improved academic performance of females at the tertiary levels. On the other hand, males' engagements in extra-curricular activities and other economic ventures, which are also linked to broader socio-economic influences such as economic hardship, financial constraints, and gendered ideologies tend to affect the academic performance of males at that level. We recommend that whilst emphasis is placed on getting more females in STEM disciplines and careers, it is equally important to focus on males. This requires continuous education and sensitisation of gender stereotypes and policy measures to sustain both males and females in STEM for overall national development. Similarities to the present study is that both of them use male and female gender in their research, on the other hand differences exist in the following areas:

Interaction Effect of Gender and Instructional Approaches and Achievement in Economics in Senior Secondary School Students

The result of the fourth hypothesis showed that there is a significant interaction effect of gender and instructional approaches on students achievement in Economics. The finding of this hypothesis is in line with the study spear, (2017) who found significant gender differences in the academic performance of students. The female students were found outperforming their male counterparts. The study also revealed that a large majority of the students scored first division or higher with relatively an outstanding performance by private schools compared to public schools. The students of private schools seem to perform better in task completion, attendance and assertiveness as well. Similarities between the reviewed literature and the present study is that both of them used male and female while their differences is that the present study is located in Taraba State, Nigeria while the reviewed study was in India. Another difference is that the reviewed study made use of both private and public schools while the present used only the public schools.

Colak, (2015) also determined the effects of competitive learning tools on medical students, Competitive learning techniques are being successfully used in courses of different disciplines. However, there is still a significant gap in analyzing their effects in medical students competing individually. The authors conducted this study to assess the effectiveness of the use of a competitive learning tool on the academic achievement and satisfaction of medical students. The authors collected data from a Human Immunology course in medical students (n = 285) and conducted a nonrandomized (quasi-experimental) control group pretest-posttest design. They used the Mann-Whitney U-test to measure the strength of the association between two variables and to compare the two student groups. The improvement and academic outcomes of the experimental group students were significantly higher than those of the control group students. The students using the competitive learning tool had better academic performance, and they were satisfied with this type of learning. The study, however, had some limitations. The authors did not make a random assignment to the control and experimental groups and the groups were not completely homogenous. The use of competitive learning techniques motivates medical students, improves their academic outcomes and may foster the cooperation among students and provide a pleasant classroom environment. The authors are planning further studies with a more complete evaluation of cognitive learning styles or incorporating chronometry as well as team-competition. The Similarities is that both of them are making use of male and female gender and also competitive learning strategy. The Differences on the other hand is that the present study is in Taraba State, Nigeria while the reviewed study was in India. Another difference is that the present study is making use of secondary school student of Economics while the reviewed made use of medical student of the university.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results and findings of the study, it was concluded that: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female Economics students exposed to cooperative learning strategy and those exposed to competitive learning strategy. There is no significant interaction effect of gender and instructional approaches on students achievement in Economics.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following were the recommendations of the study.

1. National Educational Research Development Council (NERDC) and other Government Agencies are enjoined to sponsor further researches to determine the effects of cooperative learning on students achievement in Economics in Senior Secondary Schools on a boarder perspective and to establish the findings of the present study.
2. The well to do individual and other philanthropist can as well sponsor research on this subjects matters.

Contribution to Knowledge

The contribution of this study to knowledge cannot be over-emphasized. This study had added to the number of instructional approaches that Economics Teachers can use to make the teaching and learning of Economics more meaningful and result-oriented by placing emphasis on equal opportunities to Male and Female students in the classroom.

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